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Vertical alignment of carbon nanotubes (CNTs)

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Abstract

In recent year's carbon nanotubes (CNTs), have attracted, and continue to attract, considerable interest in a wide variety of scientific files. Especially well-arranged CNTs are highly desired to prepare chemical sensors, nanoprobe for scanning probe microscopy, field emitter devices. We performed the vertical alignment of single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) in silica, mica and glass surfaces. CNTs have been functionalized successfully using microwave method, conventional sonication method, and we found out that sonication was the better technique among all of them and was confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared Microscopy (FTIR). For chemical reaction with chemical modified glass surface, the carboxylic acid groups were converted into acid chloride groups followed by the chemical reaction with chemically functionalized surfaces. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) results show the vertically aligned SWNTs, and the distribution of the vertically aligned SWNTs becomes denser as reaction time increase.

Alignment of the shorter nanotubes on the substrate increase with increase of reaction time (e.g. SWNTs of length 0.5 to 2 μ m are easy to align than the SWNTs of length 200 μ m). So we conclude that SWNTs are vertically aligned on chemically functionalized glass substrate by controlling chemical reactivity and tall and smaller diameter CNTs are difficult to align on substrate without support of neighboring Carbon Nanotubes.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, atomic force microscopy, fourier transform infrared microscopy, scanning electron microscopy

Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been widely investigated as an essential component for fabricating nanoelectronic devices and its numerous biomedical and biotechnological applications, including bone growth [1], enzyme encapsulation [2], biosensors [3, 4] and as vesicles for DNA delivery into living cells [5, 6]. Structurally, CNTs can be approximated as rolled-up sheets of graphite. Carbon nanotubes occur as two types: multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) and single-walled carbon nanotubes [7] (SWNTs). Furthermore, as the CNTs often possess chemical reactivity and surface functional groups similar to those of graphite, their properties can be tailored in an advantageous manner by chemically modifying the surface of the CNTs using an extraordinary variety of synthetic strategies. CNTs have been at the core of many studies because of their unique properties some of the basic mechanisms involved in

the electronics through CNTs, e.g. Flat Panel Displays, Various Nano devices, Nano robotics, Early Disease Diagnosis, Drug Delivery etc. IBM has recently ventured on a new project to develop transistors using these aligned CNTs. One challenge of CNTs from processing point of view is their low solubility in any solvent. Therefore, many applications utilizing CNTs require surface modification to make them amenable to processing or manipulation. To this end both covalent and non-covalent methods have been invented and recently reviewed by different groups. One challenge of CNTs (Nanolabs-USA) from processing point of view is their low solubility in any solvent. Nanomaterials have been designed for a variety.

Materials and Methods

Chemical approach for CNTs functionalization

In a typical experiment pristine SWNTs were refluxed in 4

M HNO₃ for 24 hr and filtered through a 10- μ m pore size PTFE filter paper. After filtration, the refluxed SWNTs were exposed to 1 M HCl (Lobachemi) and sonicated for half an hour for the generation of -COOH groups on the end caps and then side walls.

Alignment of CNTs means all the CNTs are directed towards a particular direction. Alignment of CNTs is subcategorized into Horizontal alignment (parallel to the surface) and Vertical alignment (perpendicular to the surface).

Vertical alignment of multi-walled carbon nanotubes has been mastered by researchers for several years. However, the growth of vertically aligned NTs (or V-NTs) on substrates has remained a challenging task. Then the cleaning of Mica, Silicon and Glass substrate was done by using solution (1:3 of hydrogen peroxide (Qualigens); sulphuric acid (Qualigens); needs mixing and gentle heat) for 30 min, rinsed in deionized water, blow dry with ultra pure nitrogen and then vacuum dry.

Sample preparation Techniques: APTES Method: Silane treatment to produce SEM

To remove the organic residue from the surface, the glass slides (1.0 cm \times 2.0 cm) were rinsed with a large amount of distilled water, then immersed in a "piranha" solution [a mixture of 70% volume concentrated sulfuric acid (98 wt %) and 30% volume of a hydrogen peroxide solution (30 wt. %)] for 30 min. The next step was to clean the glass slides were washed with a large amount of distilled water and ethanol (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), followed by dried by nitrogen gas. Then after immerse slides in a freshly prepared 2% solution for 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) (Alfa Aesar and Johnson Motthey Company, Germany) in 95% acetone for 5 seconds. Curing of the silane linkage carried out in an oven at 80^oC for 1 hour. For achieving vertical alignment two experiments are performed: MWNTs of length 0.5 to 2 μ m and diameter 20-50 nm of purity 90%, and SWNTs of length 0.5 to 2 μ m and diameter 1-2 nm of purity 95%.

Attachment of -NH₂ Group on Glass Substrate

Silane linkages with APTES on 2% in 95% aqueous acetone on glass substrate were prepared. Washed with acetone 5-7 times curing of the silane linkages carried out in an oven at 80 deg for 1 hr. Then dispersed the CNTs in pyridine suspension by sonication of 1hr at 40 deg and poured on the glass substrate.

Results and Discussion

The potential tools for the conformation of functionalization of MWNTs and SWNTs are FTIR, UV-Vis Absorption spectroscopy, and quantitative analysis using Elemental Analysis, for morphological studies SEM and AFM has been carried out. Each one has its advantages and disadvantages. SEM takes few hours time but where as AFM take days to scan one sample entirely.

To find that the MWNTs and SWNTs get functionalized, we need to go step by step, like first functional group confirmation using FTIR. The chemical functionalization can be confirmed using FTIR. The intrinsic properties of chemically functionalized MWNTs and SWNTs might have changed because of covalent attachment of functional

group. If every thing goes in a right direction then study the morphology after functionalization studied using SEM. AFM is also potential tool for the precise length and thickness measurement. But both have their own advantage and disadvantage depending on the application. SEM takes few hours to scan the entire sample, where as the AFM take day to scan the entire sample.

Functionalization of CNTs with various groups e.g. -COOH, -COCl were characterized by FTIR, the following FTIR peaks confirms the functionalization of MWNTs and SWNTs.

SEM experiments were conducted in Panjab University (P.U.); Chandigarh. SEM results shows that CNTs are aligned and results are taken at tilt of 30^o angle and 30 KV. AFM experiments were conducted in Central Scientific Instruments Organization (CSIO), Chandigarh. AFM results shows that the morphology of CNTs.

Conclusion

Vertically aligned CNTs are good alternatives to existence metallic/silicon tips for electrical applications such as field emission sources. Due to its very high aspect ratio, they exhibit good thermal stability and high electrical conductivity. This paper has described the growth of vertically aligned CNTs by chemical functionalization. First of all, CNTs have been functionalized successfully using microwave method, conventional sonication method and found out that sonication was the better technique among all of them and was confirmed by FTIR. After performing Functionalization of CNTs, Substrates are cleaned by Piranha solution, after creating -NH₂ group on substrate and -COCl group on CNTs, CNTs-pyridine suspension is poured on the substrate and kept for 24 hours to let them assemble vertically which was confirmed and characterized by SEM and AFM. Experiments are still in progress.

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